

Research Article

Liquid-Liquid Separation And Determination Of Betamethasone, Clotrimazole And Neomycin In Topical Cream By UV-Visible Spectrophotometry

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ABSTRACT

Topical creams that contain multicomponent active ingredients with antifungal, antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities are designed to treat skin infections caused by bacteria and fungi and also to inhibit inflammation produced from such infections. Amongst these agents are betamethasone propionate, clotrimazole and neomycin sulfate, often used in topical fixed-dose-combination formulations. These drugs are best assayed by HPLC, which is not easily accessed. Three brands of creams marked - I, II and III containing betamethasone dipropionate, clotrimazole and neomycin sulfate as actives were evaluated. Clotrimazole and betamethasone were extracted from cream in basic medium using DCM. Residual neomycin sulfate in basic medium was quantified by deamination using ninhydrin reagent at 570 nm, while amount of clotrimazole and betamethasone in DCM were determined by simultaneous UV spectrophotometry at 240 nm and 300 nm. The amount of CTZ, BMS and NEO in creams ranged from 96.67±0.98 to 100.33±1.69 %, 94.67±1.99 to 98.00±1.67 and 97.60±1.67 ($t = 1.624$) to 99.67±0.84 respectively. Method validation showed linearity for BMS, CTZ and NEO for concentrations ranging from 2 - 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ ($R^2 \geq 0.9996$). The slopes and intercepts of the regression equations were ≤ 0.0981 and ≤ -0.068 respectively, while calculated standard errors were ≤ 0.25 . The Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) for all brands ranged from 0.99 to 3.49 and 3.2 to 11.21 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively. The percentage recovery for BMS, CTZ and NEO in two brands ranged from 91.50±1.13 to 101.50±0.36%. Statistically, brands were adjudged to have no significant difference from amount of drugs stated on the label at 95% confidence level as the student's t-test values were found satisfactory.

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INTRODUCTION

Betamethasone propionate is fluoro-11-hydroxy-10,13,16-trimethyl-3-oxo-17-(2-propanoyloxyacetyl)-6,7,8,11,12,14,15,16-octahydrocyclopenta[a]phenanthrene-17-yl] propionate. [1] It is a synthetic corticosteroid used topically to relieve skin allergies and inflammatory conditions. It is also used in the management of asthma. [2] The anti-inflammatory activity involves the induction of peptides called lipocortins which antagonize phospholipase A2, an enzyme involved in the release arachidonic acid and eventually biosynthesis of potent endogenous inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins, leukotrienes and kinins. [3]

Clotrimazole is 1-[(2-chlorophenyl)(diphenyl)methyl]imidazole, an imidazole derivative. It is indicated for the treatment of fungal infections of the skin, vulvovaginal candidiasis and oropharyngeal candidiasis. It inhibits the growth of fungal cells by altering the permeability of the fungal cell wall. It binds to phospholipids in the cell membrane and inhibits the biosynthesis of ergosterol and other sterols required for cell membrane production. [4] Neomycin is (2R,2S,4R,5R,6R)-5-amino-2-(aminomethyl)-6-[(1R,2R,3S,4R,6S)-4,6-diamino-2-[2S,3R,4S,5R)-4-[2R,3R,4R,5S,6S,-3-amino-6-(aminomethyl)-4,5-dihydroxyoxan-2-yl]oxy-3-hydro-5-(hydroxyethyl)oxolan-2-yl]oxy-3-hydroxycyclohexyl]oxyoxane-3,4-diol. Neomycin is an aminoglycoside antibiotic found in many topical medications such as creams, ointments, and eyedrops. It contains two or more amino sugars connected by glycosidic bonds. The discovery of neomycin dates back to 1949, isolated from cultures of *Streptomyces fradiae* [1]. It has excellent activity against Gram-negative bacteria and partially effective against Gram-positive bacteria. The mechanism of action involves inhibition of protein synthesis by binding to the 30S subunit of the bacterial ribosome,

leading to misreading of the genetic code; It may also inhibit the bacterial DNA polymerase [5, 6]. The chemical structures of betamethasone propionate, clotrimazole and neomycin sulfate are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of (a) betamethasone dipropionate (b) clotrimazole (c) neomycin sulfate

A number of analytical methods for determination of betamethasone, clotrimazole and neomycin have been found in literature. These methods are either for single component [7–10], or two (and three) of the aforementioned components. [11–15] The analytical methods are by Titrimetry [7], UV Visible spectrophotometry [13–15], high performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC) [16], and by HPLC. [10, 11, 17, 18] However, the Reversed-phase LC has been described for the simultaneous determination of betamethasone and clotrimazole in cream formulations by the BP and USP [19, 20].

This study is aimed at developing simple analytical methods to assay betamethasone, clotrimazole and neomycin as components in a topical cream and assess the quality of some brands of creams sold in Yenagoa and Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

2. MATERIAS AND METHODS

2.1 Apparatus

All the spectra measurements were made using spectrumlab 755s UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Analytical weighing balance (Sartorius), micro pipette (Eperdoff) and pH meter (Orion model) were all previously calibrated.

2.2 Materials and Reagents

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. The dichloromethane was manufactured by CDH of India. The sodium hydroxide was manufactured by CHEM LIGHT of India. The disodium hydrogen orthophosphate was manufactured by BDH chemical Ltd Poole England. The ninhydrin (98.5%) was manufactured by KEM LIGHT. The reference standards neomycin sulfate (99.5%), clotrimazole (99.9%) and Betamethasone dipropionate (99.9%) were from European Directorate of Quality Medicine (EDQM), they were purchased from a vendor. The three (3) brands of topical cream BMN-Plus, MEDYSTEN and NEOSKIN, in collapsible tubes containing neomycin (0.5%, w/w), clotrimazole (1.0 %, w/w) and Betamethasone (0.05%, w/w) used for this study were purchased from reputable pharmacies in Yenagoa and Amassoma, Bayelsa State. Solutions of all reagents were freshly prepared in double distilled water.

2.2.1 Preparation of reagents

i) Ninhydrin Reagent

A 0.02M ninhydrin reagent was prepared by dissolving 0.25g of ninhydrin in 30 mL of 2% (w/v) sodium carbonate solution and making up to volume of 50ml with same solution.

ii) Sodium Carbonate Solution

A 0.02M (2% w/v) sodium carbonate solution was prepared by dissolving 0.106g of sodium carbonate in 30 ml of distilled water and made up to volume of 50 mL with distilled water.

iii) Phosphate Buffer pH 8.0

Phosphate buffer pH 8, was prepared by dissolving 2.7g of disodium hydrogen orthophosphate in 100 mL of distilled water and the pH was then adjusted to 8 with 22 mL of 0.2M NaOH solution added drop-wise using a pH meter.

2.2.2 Preparation of reference standard solutions

i) Betamethasone dipropionate standard solution

To a 50 mL volumetric flask an equivalent of 40 mg betamethasone standard was dissolved with 10 mL of dichloromethane. This was made to mark with DCM to obtain a stock solution 800µg/mL.

ii) Clotrimazole standard solution

Weight equivalent to 100 mg clotrimazole standard was transferred into a 25ml volumetric flask, dissolved with 10 mL of dichloromethane and make to mark with DCM to obtain a stock solution of 4000µg/mL.

iii) Neomycin sulphate standard

An equivalent of 50 mg Neomycin standard was transferred into a 25 mL volumetric flask and was dissolved with 5 mL of phosphate buffer solution. This was made to mark with the buffer solution to obtain a stock solution of 2000 µg /mL.

2.3 Analytical Techniques

2.3.1 Absorption spectra and determination of maximum wavelength (λ_{max}) of drugs

Betamethasone and clotrimazole spectra determination

Procedure by Vaikosen *et al.*,^[21] was adopted. Separate solutions of BMS and CTZ standards and combined standards (BMS/CTZ) were prepared in DCM from stock solutions. These solutions were scanned from 200 to 400 nm to obtain individual and combined spectra. The maximum absorptions (λ_{max}) of each drug were obtained from the spectra.

Neomycin spectrum determination

To an equivalent concentration of 20 ug/ml neomycin (NEO) in a 10 ml volumetric flask, 2ml of ninhydrin solution was added, heated (56 ° C) for 2–3 minutes, allowed to cool and made to mark with the buffer solution. The resultant purple colour was scanned in the visible region from 400 to 800 nm to obtain maximum absorption for NEO.

2.4 Calibration curve of Neomycin Sulphate

Five working concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50ug/mL were prepared from stock solution in 10 mL volumetric flask, 2 mL of ninhydrin solution was added to each and exposed to heat (56 °C) in a water bath for 2–3 minutes. The mixture was allowed to cool, made to mark with the buffer solution and absorbance was measured at 570 nm. The calibration graph was plotted from the values obtained.

2.5 Procedure for separation, simultaneous extraction and application of methods to drugs

2.5.1 Extraction and separation of drugs

From the cream, 2.0 g was transferred into 25 mL phosphate buffer solution in a 250 mL separating funnel. The mixture was homogenized and shaken gently with 20 mL of dichloromethane (DCM) for 5 minutes and allowed to separate into aqueous and organic phases. The organic phase was collected into a 100 ml beaker and the aqueous phase was further extracted with 2 x 20 mL dichloromethane. All DCM extracts were pooled together in a 100ml beaker (This portion contains betamethasone and clotrimazole). The aqueous phase was transferred into a 50 mL volumetric flask and made to mark with the buffer solution and was kept for the estimation of neomycin content in the sample.

2.5.1.1 Quantification of Neomycin

To 3 mL aliquot of the aqueous phase in a 10mL volumetric flask, 2 mL of ninhydrin solution was added and exposed to heat (56°C) for 2–3 minutes. The mixture was allowed to cool and made to mark with the buffer solution. The absorbance was then measured at 570nm.

2.5.1.2 Simultaneous quantification of betamethasone and clotrimazole

The combined dichloromethane layer was filtered through a bed of anhydrous sodium sulfate. The DCM extract was evaporated on a steam bath to 20mL, cooled and transferred into a 25mL volumetric flask, made to mark and the absorbance was measured at 240 nm and 300 nm.

The amount of betamethasone and clotrimazole were then calculated using the simultaneous equation below.

$$A_1 = eb_1cb + ez_1cz$$

$$A_2 = eb_2cb + ez_2cz$$

Where;

A_1 = Absorbance of Mixture at 240nm

A_2 = Absorbance of Mixture at 300nm

eb_1 = Absorptivity of Betamethasone at 240nm

eb_2 = Absorptivity of Betamethasone at 300nm

ez_1 = Absorptivity of Clotrimazole at 240nm

ez_2 = Absorptivity of Clotrimazole at 300nm

cb = Concentration of Betamethasone

cz = Concentration of Clotrimazole

2.4 Method validation

The ICH guidelines [22] was used to assess the analytical performances of methods, furthermore they were applied to formulated brands with the same multicomponent actives. Methods were assessed based on parameters; such as sensitivity, specificity, interference, linearity, precision, accuracy, ruggedness and robustness in accordance to the guidelines.

A five point calibration curve was made to assess the linearity and sensitivity of the methods, while the regression equations and other parameters were obtained using the least squares method. Method sensitivity was assessed by determining the limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ); using the expressions, $LOD = 3.3S_a/b$; $LOQ = 10 S_a/b$ (where S_a = standard deviation of the intercept; b = the slope of the regression line). [23, 24] The ruggedness and reliability of the methods for routine laboratory quality assessment was evaluated by assaying different brands of topical cream using proposed methods. Recovery studies were carried out by standard addition technique using sample and spiked concentrations totalling 12, 15, 20 and 25 mg for BMS and NEO, while for CTZ, total amount of drugs were 3, 4, 6 and 8 mg. The accuracy and precision were based on the standard deviation (SD), relative standard

deviation (RSD) and standard error of the mean (SEM). The drugs were replicated thrice on the same day (intraday), while the inter-day assay was done within a week for 3 days at every-other-day (interday), using the same concentrations and two brands of the cream.

4.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Absorption spectra and determination of maximum wavelength (λ_{max}) of drugs

Figure 2 shows scanned spectra of betamethasone, clotrimazole and combined drugs standards. Betamethasone showed absorptions at 240nm and 300nm, while clotrimazole at 240 nm only. However, two distinct peaks were observed at 240 and 300nm for the combined drugs, with a maxima at the former – this is reflective of the individual spectra for betamethasone and clotrimazole. Spectra of both drugs showed overlaps and overlains, thus making the use of simultaneous or derivative UV spectroscopy very imperative for their quantification. The absorption at 240 nm for betamethasone agrees with maximum wavelength reported by Bachri *et al.*, [13] The scanned spectrum of the derivatized neomycin–ninhydrin complex showed maximum absorption at 570 nm (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Spectra of betamethasone (20 µg/mL), clotrimazole (4 µg/mL) and combined drugs standards (CTZ + BMS)

Table 1: Optimum conditions for drug assay by proposed methods

PARAMETER	Clotrimazole	Betamethasone	Neomycin
Wavelength (nm)	240, 300	240, 300	570
Beer's conc. range ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	10 - 50	2 - 10	10 - 50
Limit of detection (LOD) ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	1.25	0.99	3.49

Figure 3: Spectrum of derivatized neomycin–ninhydrin complex

Analytical performance

Linearity, range and sensitivity

Table I, shows the optima conditions exhibited by proposed methods for CTZ, BMS and NEO. The calibration curves for BMS and NEO standards, showed good linearity at concentrations ranging from 10 – 50 µg/mL, while for CTZ it was from 2 – 10 µg/mL. The correlation coefficient (R^2) for CTZ, BMS and NEO were 0.9996, 0.9999 and 0.9998 respectively, within the working concentrations. The regression equations were obtained using Origin 8 software. The intercept and slope for NEO were – 0.068 and 0.0177 respectively, corresponding values of 0.003 and 0.0051 for BMS, while CTZ was 0.0026 and 0.0981 respectively ($n = 5$). These values imply high sensitivity of the proposed methods. The LOD values for the drugs ranged from 0.99 – 3.49 µg/mL, while the LOQ was 3.27 – 11.21 µg/mL. These values simply confirmed the repeatability and reliability of the applied methods.

Limit of quantification (LOQ) ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	4.13	3.27	11.21
<u>Regression equation</u>			
Slope	0.0051	0.0981	0.0177
Intercept	0.0030	0.0027	-0.068
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.9996	0.9999	0.9998

Precision and accuracy

The intra-day and inter-day precision for proposed methods are presented in Table 2. The relative standard deviations (%RSD, $n = 3$) for drug components in topical creams ranged from 0.2 - 1.78 % for intra-day precision, while the inter-day precision was from 0.40 – 1.77%. The standard

errors of the mean (SEM) for all analytes and methods were ≤ 0.25 for all runs. These values portrays high reproducibility, with the precision and accuracy of methods found satisfactory.

Table 2: Summary of Precision and accuracy studies for spectroscopic method

Intra-day assay (n = 3)		Amount of drug ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)				
Brand I	Taken	Found \pm SD	RSD (%)	SEM	Amount Found (%)	
Clotrimazole	4	3.85 \pm 0.04	1.17	0.03	96.33 \pm 1.12	
	6	5.97 \pm 0.10	1.71	0.06	99.44 \pm 1.70	
	8	7.99 \pm 0.04	0.56	0.03	99.83 \pm 0.56	
	10	10.09 \pm 0.10	0.97	0.06	100.87 \pm 0.97	
(Mean content, %)					99.12 \pm 1.09	
Betamethasone	10	9.47 \pm 0.16	1.68	0.09	94.73 \pm 1.59	
	15	14.97 \pm 0.08	0.52	0.04	99.82 \pm 0.52	
	20	19.99 \pm 0.08	0.40	0.05	99.95 \pm 0.40	
	25	24.67 \pm 0.44	1.78	0.25	98.68 \pm 1.75	
(Mean content, %)					98.30 \pm 1.07	
Neomycin	10	9.81 \pm 0.09	0.94	0.05	98.13 \pm 0.92	
	15	14.88 \pm 0.06	0.43	0.04	99.18 \pm 0.42	
	20	19.87 \pm 0.06	0.31	0.04	99.37 \pm 0.31	
	25	25.01 \pm 0.05	0.20	0.03	100.04 \pm 0.20	
(Mean content, %)					99.18 \pm 0.46	
Inter-day assay (n = 3)						
Brand I						
Clotrimazole	4	3.87 \pm 0.03	0.68	0.02	96.67 \pm 0.66	
	6	5.93 \pm 0.06	1.04	0.04	98.83 \pm 1.03	
	8	7.97 \pm 0.04	0.54	0.02	99.63 \pm 0.54	
	10	10.01 \pm 0.09	0.94	0.05	100.07 \pm 0.94	
(Mean content, %)					98.80 \pm 0.79	
Betamethasone	10	9.88 \pm 0.16	1.58	0.09	98.80 \pm 1.56	
	15	14.90 \pm 0.08	0.53	0.05	99.36 \pm 0.53	
	20	20.13 \pm 0.24	1.22	0.14	100.63 \pm 1.22	
	25	24.80 \pm 0.10	0.40	0.06	99.20 \pm 0.40	
(Mean content, %)					99.50 \pm 0.93	
Neomycin	10	9.68 \pm 0.14	1.49	0.08	96.80 \pm 1.44	
	15	14.84 \pm 0.07	0.48	0.04	98.93 \pm 0.47	
	20	20.24 \pm 0.32	1.59	0.19	101.18 \pm 1.61	

	25	23.82 ± 0.42	1.77	0.24	95.29 ± 1.69
(Mean content, %)					98.05 ± 1.30

Robustness and recovery studies

Varying some experimental conditions using two brands of topical cream and the addition of pure CTZ, NEO and BMS were used to assess the robustness and reliability under the recovery studies (Table 3). Calculated percent recovery for CTZ, BMS and NEO ranged from 91.50±1.13 – 99.33±1.09%, 93.93±1.74 – 101.50 ± 0.36%,

and 93.47± 0.26 – 100.50 ± 0.72% respectively for both brands assessed. These values shows that varying of brands and working concentrations would not have any significant consequence in applying the proposed methods and hence they were considered robust and reliable for routine analysis of CTZ, BMS and NEO in topical creams.

Table 3: Recovery studies for clotrimazole, betamethasone and neomycin in topical cream

Analyte drug in topical cream	BRAND I				BRAND II			
	Amount of drug in weighed cream (mg)	Amount of pure drug spiked (mg)	Total quantity of drug found (mg)	Percent recovery of drug added (%)	Amount of drug in weighed cream (mg)	Amount of pure drug spiked (mg)	Total quantity of drug found (mg)	Percent recovery of drug added (%)
Clotrimazole	1	2	2.86±0.05	93.17±1.79	1	2	2.96±0.05	98.00±1.71
	2	2	3.95±0.05	97.50±1.24	2	2	3.83±0.05	91.50±1.13
	3	3	5.95±0.05	98.44±0.77	3	3	5.92±0.09	97.33±1.55
	4	4	8.01±0.06	100.17±0.75	4	4	7.97±0.09	99.33 ± 1.09
Betamethasone	10	2	11.98±0.12	99.17±1.02	10	2	12.03±0.04	101.50±0.36
	12.5	2.5	14.88±0.08	95.33±0.53	12.5	2.5	14.89±0.08	95.47±0.50
	15	5	19.82±0.23	96.40±1.15	15	5	20.01±0.06	100.27±0.28
	15	10	24.39±0.35	93.93±1.74	15	10	24.96±0.04	99.60±0.18
Neomycin	10	2	11.89±0.05	94.50±0.40	10	2	12.01±0.09	100.50±0.72
	12.5	2.5	14.84±0.04	93.47±0.26	12.5	2.5	14.88±0.08	95.33±0.53
	15	5	19.79±0.16	95.73±0.77	15	5	19.92±0.06	98.40±0.32
	15	10	24.55±0.26	95.53±1.30	15	10	24.89±0.01	98.93±0.06

Assay of dosage form

Three brands of topical creams (Brand I, Brand II and Brand III) containing CTZ, BMS and NEO were assayed applying the proposed spectrophotometric methods. Table 4, shows the results obtained for the components in different brands. The pharmacopeia specification for CTZ, BMS and NEO in topical creams ranges from 90.0 to 110.0% of the quantity claimed. [19, 20] The

amounts of drugs found in the samples were within the specified range and were in good agreement with label claims on the brands. The percentage content of CTZ in the three brands ranged from 96.67 ± 0.98% to 100.33± 1.69, while amount in BMS and NEO ranged from 94.67 ± 1.99% to 98.00 ± 1.67% and 97.60 ± 1.67 to 99.67 ± 0.84% respectively.

Table 4: Application of methods to topical cream formulation

Brands/ Drugs	Label claim (% w/w/tube)	Amt. found \pm SD (% w/w /tube)	RSD (%)	SEM	Amt. found \pm SD (mg/tube)	Content (%)
Brand I						
Clotrimazole	1.0	0.97 \pm 0.01	0.94	0.01	0.290 \pm 0.003	96.67 \pm 0.98 (t = 0.9421)
Betamethasone	0.05	0.049 \pm 0.001	1.63	0.001	0.015 \pm 0.000	98.00 \pm 1.67 (t = 0.8246)
Neomycin	0.5	0.490 \pm 0.01	1.31	0.004	0.147 \pm 0.002	98.07 \pm 1.34 (t = 1.0524)
Brand II						
Clotrimazole	1.0	0.98 \pm 0.01	1.25	0.01	0.293 \pm 0.004	97.67 \pm 1.28 (t = 0.7246)
Betamethasone	0.05	0.048 \pm 0.001	1.63	0.001	0.014 \pm 0.000	96.00 \pm 1.70 (t = 1.9713)
Neomycin	0.5	0.498 \pm 0.01	0.84	0.002	0.150 \pm 0.001	99.67 \pm 0.84 (t = 1.624)
Brand III						
Clotrimazole	1.0	1.0 \pm 0.01	1.70	0.01	0.301 \pm 0.005	100.33 \pm 1.69 (t = 0.8110)
Betamethasone	0.05	0.047 \pm 0.001	1.89	0.001	0.015 \pm 0.000	94.67 \pm 1.99 (t = 1.0723)
Neomycin	0.5	0.488 \pm 0.01	1.63	0.005	0.146 \pm 0.001	97.60 \pm 1.67 (t = 1.624)

Student *t*-test is with respect to the label claim of each drugs; *t*-distribution at 95% confidence limits is 4.303 for n = 3 and 2 degrees of freedom.

Also, the student's *t*-test values for the three analytes CTZ, BMS and NEO in the cream were \leq 1.971, compared to the tabulated value of 4.303 for 3 replicates at 95% confidence. This implies that there was no significant difference between the label claim on each brand and values obtained in applying the proposed methods. [25]

4.2 CONCLUSION

The proposed method was successfully applied to the analysis of clotrimazole, betamethasone and neomycin in fixed-dose combination in topical creams. The three components were successfully extracted/separated into basic aqueous and DCM phases, with the latter containing clotrimazole and betamethasone and the neomycin in basic phase. Statistically, method was adjudged satisfactory as there was no significant difference between the label claim and amount found in three samples. The reliability, precision and accuracy of the proposed method are reflected in the validation parameters assessed and could be used for the quality assessment of clotrimazole, betamethasone and neomycin in FDC creams.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The study does not involve the use of animals or human participant by any of the authors

- Consent for publication

All authors gave their consent that manuscript should be published in Pharmaceutical Journal

- Availability of data and material
All data obtained in this study are included in the present manuscript
- Competing/Conflict of interests
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- Authors' contributions

Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT)

Edebi N. Vaikosen: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software; Data curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology; Validation; Visualization; Writing

Ruth C. Worlu: Data curation; Formal Investigation; Validation; Visualization; Writing

Samuel J. Bunu: Software; Data curation; Formal analysis; Validation; Visualization

Ebiere Dode: Formal analysis; Validation; Visualization

Mary Doctor: Formal analysis; Investigation; Writing - original draft

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